

STUDIES ON SYNTHETIC ESTROGENS. PART II

BY H. SINGH AND R. S. KAPIL*

Several 2-*p*-chloro- and 2-*p*-bromo-benzoylbenzofurans have been synthesised as possible estrogenic compounds.

In a recent communication (Singh and Kapil, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 2064) preparation of a number of 2-*p*-anisoylbenzofurans as possible estrogens has been described. The studies have now been extended to certain 2-*p*-chloro- and 2-*p*-bromo-benzoylbenzofuran derivatives. All of them have been prepared by condensing potassium salts of the appropriate hydroxy-ketones with *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromo-phenacyl bromides in ethanol (vide Tables I and II).

The substituted benzofurans, prepared, are colorless crystalline solids, insoluble in water and alkalis, and soluble in ethanol and acetic acid. It is noteworthy that 3-methyl-substituted compounds are much less soluble than the corresponding 3-ethylbenzofurans. The yields of the 3-methyl-substituted benzofurans, in general, are better than the corresponding 3-ethyl-substituted compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL**

o-Hydroxyketones required in the synthesis were prepared through the Fries migration (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4271).

2-*p*-Chloro- and 2-*p*-bromo-benzoylbenzofurans were prepared by the procedure described earlier (Singh and Kapil, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

2-*p*-Chlorobenzoylbenzofurans.

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.P.	Formula.	% Halogen	
								Found	Calc.
1.	Me	H	H	Cl	H	142°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂	Cl: 23.1	23.2
2.	"	H	Cl	H	H	125°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₃	Cl: 23.0	23.2
3.	"	H	Me	H	Br	190°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ ClBr	Cl + Br: 31.7	31.8
4.	"	Cl	H	H	Cl	156°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ Cl ₃	Cl: 31.1	31.3
5.	"	H	Cl	Cl	H	177°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ Cl ₃	Cl: 31.2	31.3
6.	"	H	Br	H	Cl	214°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br	Cl + Br: 39.0	39.3
7.	"	H	Cl	H	Br	120°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br	Cl + Br: 39.1	39.3
8.	Et	H	Br	H	Cl	140°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br	Cl + Br: 37.8	37.9

N.B. All the compounds were recrystallised from AcOH-EtOH excepting No. 8, which was recrystallised from EtOH.

* Present address: Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

** All melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE II

2-p-Bromobenzoylbenzofurans.

No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.P.	Formula.	% Halogen.	
								Found.	Calc.
1.	Me	H	Me	H	H	145°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ Br	Br: 24.1	24.3
2.	..	H	H	Cl	H	132°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ ClBr	Cl + Br: 32.9	33.0
3.	..	H	Cl	H	H	130°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ ClBr	Cl + Br: 32.8	33.0
4.	..	H	Br	H	H	125°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ Br ₂	Br: 40.4	40.6
5.	..	H	Me	H	Br	186°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ Br ₂	Br: 39.1	39.2
6.	..	H	Cl	Cl	H	167°	C ₁₆ H ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br	Cl + Br: 39.2	39.3
7.	..	H	Br	H	Cl	173°	C ₁₆ H ₈ O ₂ ClBr ₂	Cl + Br: 45.5	45.6
8.	Et	H	Cl	H	H	115°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ ClBr	Cl + Br: 31.6	31.7
9.	..	H	Br	H	H	175°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ Br ₂	Br: 39.0	39.2
10.	..	H	Br	H	Cl	160°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ ClBr ₂	Cl + Br: 44.0	44.1

N.B. Compounds No. 1—7 were recrystallised from AcOH-EtOH and the rest from EtOH.

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., for his kind interest in this work.

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

Received August 3, 1960.